

Effects of Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy on Serum Alt Levels

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Abstract

Background: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy (LC) is considered to be the gold standard treatment option for cholelithiasis. Various studies have shown that LC causes elevation in serum levels of certain hepatic enzymes.

Objective: The objective of this study was to compare the mean pre-operative levels of serum Alanine Transaminase (ALT) with mean post-operative levels of serum Alanine Transaminase after Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in tertiary care hospital of Rawalpindi.

Materials & methods: This single group experimental study was conducted from January 2017 to March 2017 at Surgical Unit 1 of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. 44 patients with confirmed diagnosis of cholelithiasis undergoing LC were included. Their pre-op serum ALT levels were investigated. Immediately after LC, serum ALT levels were repeated to determine post-op serum ALT levels. Data was analyzed with SPSS v22 and in addition to descriptive statistics; Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test for paired data was applied at 5% level of significance.

Results: After LC, serum ALT levels increased in 82%, decreased in 14% while remained same in 4% of the patients. Post-op Derangement of serum ALT levels (>43u/l) was observed in 50% of the patients, with normal baselines, undergoing LC. Mean Pre-op ALTs observed were 28±10 u/l while mean post-op ALTs were 42±15 u/l. Mean change observed between Pre op and Post op ALTs of patients after LC was 14±12 u/l. There was highly significant difference in mean pre-op and mean post-op serum ALT levels with P value 0.00. Results were

statistically extremely significant. No relation between elevation of serum ALT levels and gender could be established (P value 0.103) while derangement of ALT levels (>43u/l) was observed more in male than in female patients. Mean change in ALT levels after LC increased proportionally with age.

Conclusion: Significant change was observed in serum levels of ALT which suggests that pneumoperitoneum created during LC causes hepatocellular ischemia leading to cellular injury which might be the cause of elevation in serum ALT level.

Key words: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy, Serum ALT levels, Pneumoperitoneum

Introduction

For over 25 years, Open Cholecystectomy (OC) has been replaced by Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy (LC). And now Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a gold standard surgical procedure for gallbladder operation. ¹ Although LC has many advantages over laparotomy and OC, its effects on cardiovascular and respiratory system are being questioned.² Creating pneumoperitoneum is an integral part of LC. Pneumoperitoneum has been stated to cause transient reduction in hepatic blood flow³ Pneumoperitoneum pressure and duration of exposure to it have been stated to have relationship with the extent of elevation of serum levels of hepatic enzymes.^{4,5} Serum ALT levels are considered to be an indicator of hepatocellular damage.^{6,7} Post-operative elevation in serum ALT levels after LC suggests that some hepatocellular damage might have occurred.⁸ The elevation in serum levels of liver enzymes is a

transient phenomenon and LFTs return to normal range spontaneously.^{9,10} Many factors including pneumoperitoneum have been stated to be the contributors of the hemodynamic changes leading to changes in serum levels of liver enzymes.¹¹ Gas less LC using abdominal retractors has also been proposed but it hasn't proved to be any superior to the conventional methods.¹² Various studies have shown that LC is associated with elevation in serum levels of certain hepatic enzymes like ALT, AST, LDH and TSB.¹³⁻¹⁵ The objective of this study was to compare the mean pre-operative levels of serum alanine transaminase with mean post-operative levels of serum Alanine Transaminase after laparoscopic cholecystectomy in a tertiary care hospital of Rawalpindi.

Materials & Methods

This single group experimental study was conducted from January 2017 to March 2017 at Surgical Unit 1 of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.

A total of 44 (12 male and 32 female) patients with suspected diagnosis of cholelithiasis were included.

Provisional diagnosis of cholelithiasis was based upon history, examination serum bilirubin levels and liver function tests. Diagnosis was confirmed by interpreting abdominal ultrasounds. 2cc blood was drawn from ante cubital vein after taking aseptic measures. These blood samples, drawn within 12 hours of procedure, were used to determine the baseline serum ALT levels of the patients with confirmed diagnosis of cholelithiasis. Blood was centrifuged for 3-5 minutes, using Rotofix-32 machine. To determine ALT levels, Beckman Coulter AU-480 automation machine was used. In pre-op rooms, vitals of patients were maintained within normal limit and carefully monitored for 24 hours, Patients' fitness for general anesthesia was assessed and then similar anesthesia techniques were followed for all the patients.

Under general anesthesia, standard 4 port laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed. Pneumoperitoneum was established with closed technique with veress needle. CO₂ pneumoperitoneum pressure was maintained between 8mmHg to 14mmHg for 30-40 minutes. 10mm umbilical, 10mm epigastric, 5mm right hypochondrial and 5mm right lumbar port were inserted. Within 12 hours, 2cc blood was again drawn from antecubital vein following the same procedure to determine post-op ALT levels. Data of patients like age, gender, pre-op and post-op ALT levels was recorded and then was analyzed with SPSS v22.

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were applied to check for normality of distribution of data. Q-Q plots were made for pre-op and post-op serum ALT levels for the confirmation purpose. In addition to descriptive statistics; Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test for paired data was applied at 5% level of significance. Data was divided into three groups. The ones with Pre-op ALT levels > Post-op ALT levels, with Pre-op ALT levels = Post-op ALT levels, with Pre-op ALT levels < Post-op ALT levels. Paired sample "t" test was applied to compare mean pre-op ALT levels with mean post-op ALT levels.

Results

After LC, serum ALT levels increased in 82% (83.4% males, 75% females) , decreased in 14% (0% males, 12.5% females) while remained same in 4% (16.7% males, 12.5% females) patients (Table I). Mean pre-op ALT levels were 28±10 u/l while mean post-op ALT levels were 42±15 u/l. Mean difference observed between Pre-op and Post-op ALT levels was 14±12 u/l. Student "t" test was applied to compare mean pre-op and mean post-op serum ALT levels. The difference was statistically highly significant (p=0.000) (Table 2). Wilcoxon signed rank test was applied to distribute data into positive ranks, negative ranks and ties between pre-op and post-op ALT levels. Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were applied to check for normality of distribution of data. The data was normally distributed. Q-Q plots for pre-op and post-op ALT levels were also applied for the verification of results of normality of distribution of data. No relation between elevation of serum ALT levels and gender could be established (P value 0.103) while derangement of ALT levels (>43u/l) was observed more in male (66.7%) than in female (43.8%) patients (Graph I). Mean change in ALT levels after LC increased proportionally with age (Graph II).

Table I: Gender-wise Comparison of Post-Op serum ALT levels

Post-operative serum ALT values	MALE		FEMALE	
	COUNT	%males	COUNT	%females
Increased	2	16.7%	10	31.2%
Deranged (>43u/l)	8	66.7%	14	43.8%
Decreased	0	0.0%	4	12.5%
Remained same	2	16.7%	4	12.5%

Table II: Comparison of Pre-Op and Post-Op Mean Serum ALT levels

		Pre-op serum ALT levels	Post-op serum ALT levels	Change (Pre-op - Post-op ALT levels)
Mean ± Std. Dev.		27.91±10.07	42.18±14.88	14.32±12.33
Range		40	61	41
Minimum		13	16	-9
Maximum		53	77	32
95% Confidence interval of the difference	Max			18.01
	Min			10.54
P-value				0.0001

GRAPH I: Gender-wise distribution Post-Op serum ALT levels

GRAPH II: Mean change in serum ALT levels after Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in various age groups

Discussion

Elevation of serum ALT levels was once considered accidental. But previous studies have developed a

significant relation between laparoscopic cholecystectomy and hepatic enzymes. It has been established that significant elevation in serum levels of ALT, AST, LDH and TSB is seen after laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

We found that serum ALT levels increased in 82% of the patients after LC. Various other studies have also stated the elevation of serum ALT levels in more than 80% patients.^{16,20}

No relation between gender of the patient and elevation of serum ALT levels could be established which is also in accordance with the previously done studies.^{17,18}

CO₂ pneumoperitoneum, liver retraction for better exposure, manipulation of bile ducts, cauterization of liver bed to stop bleeding and general anesthesia are considered to be the possible causes for the post-op elevation of hepatic enzymes.¹⁴

Liver retraction for better exposure, manipulation of bile ducts, cauterization of liver bed and general anesthesia are routinely performed in open cholecystectomy as well.⁸ Still the changes in liver enzymes are less frequently observed and less marked in OC.^{10,19}

The only apparent variable in LC is the creation of pneumoperitoneum. Normally the pneumoperitoneum pressure is maintained between 8mmHg and 14mmHg. It has been stated that pneumoperitoneum pressure causes hepatic ischemia and hence liver injury.^{3,9,10,12}

Portal vein is the major contributor in hepatic blood flow and the normal portal venous pressure is 7-10mmHg. Jakimovicz showed that pneumoperitoneum pressure of 14mmHg reduced hepatic blood flow by 53%. These results were obtained through Doppler technique to determine hepatic perfusion after creation of pneumoperitoneum.¹² Decrease in hepatic blood flow leads to ischemia of hepatic parenchyma and damage to Kupffer cells and endothelial cells of hepatic sinusoids.²²

In studies conducted to compare post-operative elevation of hepatic enzymes between laparoscopic and open cholecystectomy in patients who were given same antibiotics & anesthetics, it has been observed that the changes in serum levels of hepatic enzymes are more significant in LC than in OC.^{10,19}

It has been established that the degree of elevation of hepatic enzymes is associated with the duration of exposure to pneumoperitoneum. Duration of surgery had no effect on the elevation of hepatic enzymes in patients undergoing open cholecystectomy.^{4,5}

It has been observed that when duration of exposure to pneumoperitoneum exceeds 60 minutes, the changes in serum levels of hepatic enzymes become highly significant.¹³

Hasukic conducted a randomized study to compare the effects of high pressure and low-pressure pneumoperitoneum on liver functions. It was observed that post-operative serum ALT elevations were significantly higher in patients who were operated under high pressure pneumoperitoneum.⁷

Girauda conducted a study to compare the changes in serum levels of hepatic enzymes in LC, low pressure LC and gasless LC. Girauda found that the significant post-operative elevation in serum levels of hepatic enzymes was not observed in low pressure LC and gasless LC.⁸

However, these changes in serum levels of ALT after LC are a transient phenomenon.¹³ Time controlled studies have shown that these changes last for about 3 days postoperatively and have not been reported to be clinically important.^{6-8,17} We also did not encounter any complications in patients undergoing LC and having deranged post-operative serum ALT levels.

Although LC is considered to be high risk in patients with Child Pugh Class C (decompensated) liver, the relation of increased mortality in such patients during LC has not been developed with pneumoperitoneum yet.²²

Although these changes are transient and their clinical importance is yet to be established, care should be taken when making a decision to perform LC in patients with hepatic insufficiency. In such patients, low pressure LC or gasless LC using abdominal retractors, can be performed.

Conclusion

We conclude that significant change was observed in serum levels of ALT post operatively, which suggests that pneumoperitoneum created during LC could be causing hepatocellular ischemia leading to cellular injury causing elevation in serum ALT level.

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